

KP programme-specific SSLN learning activities and participation

Learning modality	Number	Participation	Notes
Webinars	13	250 participants per webinar	All webinars were organised in collaboration with KP Community of Practice supported by GPC. Dedicated session led by KP community networks in each webinar
Films on KP programming	3	Co-produced with KP-led organisations	Documented KP community-led practice
Case studies	8	4 specifically featured KP-led organisations	Documented practices implemented by KP led organisations
Link-and-learn sessions	20	All sessions included KP representatives	Topics informed by KP pillar PSAT priorities
Inter-country learning visits	8	KP representatives were included in all learning visit delegations	Most visits focused on harm reduction programming for people who use drugs, an emerging programming area in Africa
Technical support initiatives	6	2 technical support initiatives provided targeted support to strengthen KP networks	Focused capacity support to networks
In person meetings and workshops	6	All in-person meetings included country and global KP representatives; a 2024 Ghana meeting had 50% participation from KP networks	In-person KP peer learning and special spaces created within the meetings

10.5281/zenodo.20797774